

Chlorophenoxyacetic Acids and their Derivatives as Possible Tuberculostats*

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The hydrazides and their condensation products with eleven aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes of the three auxins, 4-chloro-, 2,4-dichloro-, and 2,4,5-trichloro-phenoxyacetic acids, and their glycine and ($\pm$)-methionine conjugates have been prepared and screened for *in vitro* activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v strain. Out of the 119 compounds screened, 41 have been found to inhibit the growth of the organism *in vitro* at a dilution of 1 in 10,000.

Synthetic auxins were tested for their tuberculostatic activity, perhaps for the first time, by Dubos¹. Later investigations²⁻⁶ on similar lines have indicated that auxin derivatives may be developed into potential tuberculostats.

In a quest for possible new tuberculostats, several pyridoylamino-acids and derivatives⁷, acetyl dipeptides⁸, and derivatives of pyridine and furan⁹ have been synthesised and screened for *in vitro* antitubercular activity with encouraging results.

In an extended effort, the hydrazides and their condensation products with eleven aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes (Table IV) of the three auxins, 4-chloro-, 2,4-dichloro-, and 2,4,5-trichloro-phenoxyacetic acids and their glycine and ($\pm$)-methionine conjugates have been synthesised and screened for antitubercular activity against the virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, H₃₇R_v, and the results reported in this communication. The general scheme for the present work has been as follows:

[R=4-Cl.C₆H₄- or 2,4-Cl₂.C₆H₃- or 2,4,5-Cl₃.C₆H₂-; R'=H or H₃CS.CH₂.CH₂-; R''= aldehyde residue].

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1. *Proc. Soc., Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1946, 63, 317.
2. Youmans and Youmans, *J. Bact.*, 1948, 56, 52.
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5. Offe *et al.*, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1952, 7b, 446.
6. Ignatova and Goryaev, *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, 58, 3341.
7. Nigam, Iyer and Sirsi, Proceedings of the Symposium (1959) on Chemotherapy, published by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India, pp. 28-31; S. N. Nigam, Ph. D. thesis, Agra University, 1959.
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In series A, the auxins (Type I) were converted successively into ethyl esters (Type II), hydrazides (Type III), and aldehyde-condensation products (Type IV) of the hydrazides. In series B, the auxins were condensed with the ethyl esters of glycine and ($\pm$)-methionine, using *NN'*-dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide(DCC) to obtain the corresponding amino-acid conjugate esters (Type V) which were then converted successively into hydrazides (Type VI) and their aldehyde-condensation products (Type VII). The aldehyde-condensation products (Types IV and VII) are recorded in Tables I-III. The results of screening for tuberculostatic activity are shown in Table IV.

Out of the 119 compounds screened, 41 inhibited the *in vitro* growth *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v at a dilution of 1:10,000. This study has led to the following structure-activity relationship in this series of compounds. For the purpose of discussing data presented in Table IV, "activity" and "no activity" denote "complete inhibition" and "no inhibition" respectively of the *in vitro* growth of the tubercle bacillus at 1:10,000 dilution. It should, however, be noted that several compounds, other than those indicated in Table IV, have shown partial activity.

(i) While the hydrazides of all the three auxins are active, only two out of 6 six hydrazides of amino-acid conjugates of the auxins are active.

(ii) Some of the aldehyde-condensation products of the inactive conjugate hydrazides are active, despite inactivity of the related aldehyde *per se*.

(iii) Out of the 98 aldehyde-condensation products, 33 are active, 21 of the latter being pyridine aldehyde derivatives, indicating optimum occurrence of activity in this series.

(iv) The number and position of chlorine atoms have no uniform effect on the activity.

*EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid was prepared by condensing 4-chlorophenol with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali¹⁰, but 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) was prepared from its sodium salt which, as also 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4,5-T), was kindly presented to us by Messrs. Agramore Ltd., Bangalore. The known esters (Type II) and hydrazides (Type III) were prepared by the usual methods. DCC was prepared, starting from cyclohexylamine¹¹.

*Ethyl 4-Chlorophenoxyacetyl*glycinate (Type V).—Ethyl glycinate (5.5 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (20 ml) and to this solution was added a solution of DCC (11.3 g.) in dioxane (25 ml). When 4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (9.96 g.), dissolved in dioxane (30 ml), was added to the above mixture and shaken, a white precipitate of dicyclohexylurea separated. The coupling mixture was left overnight at the room temperature. The excess of DCC was decomposed with a few drops of acetic acid and the mixture left for an hour more. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless crystals, m.p. 89°. (Found: N, 5.30. C₁₂H₁₄O₄NCl requires N, 5.15%).

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

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11. Okawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1956, **29**, 488.

CHLOROPHENOXYACETIC ACIDS & DERIVATIVES AS POSSIBLE TUBERCULOSTATS

TABLE I

Chlorophenoxyacetyl derivatives.

R'	M.P.	I. R=4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .		II. R=2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .		III. R=2,4,5-Cl ₃ .C ₆ H ₂ .	
		Formula,	%Nitrogen, Found. Reqd.	Formula,	%Nitrogen, Found. Reqd.	Formula,	%Nitrogen, Found. Reqd.
C ₆ H ₅ .	191°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	9.72 9.71	*C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	9.15 8.67	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	8.23 7.93
3,4-(O.CH ₂ .O).C ₆ H ₃ .	210-11°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	8.66 8.42	*C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	7.53 7.63	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₃	7.33 6.98
<i>p</i> -Me ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .	210°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	13.05 12.07	*C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	11.68 11.48	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	10.08 10.48
<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .	225°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.02 9.20	*C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₄	8.25 8.20	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃	7.84 7.51
<i>p</i> -MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .	186°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.14 8.79	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	8.18 7.93	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	7.56 7.23
<i>p</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .	196-97°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.10 13.84	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	12.77 12.43	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	11.48 11.27
C ₆ H ₅ .CH=CH-	212°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.20 8.90	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	8.19 8.02	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃	7.54 7.30
C ₃ H ₇ N-2.	168-70°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.46 14.51	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	13.01 12.00	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	12.10 11.71
C ₃ H ₇ N-3.	161-63°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.55 14.51	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	13.02 12.06	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	11.87 11.71
C ₃ H ₇ N-4.	144-45°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.19 14.51	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	13.13 12.06	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	11.93 11.71
C ₉ H ₉ N-2.	203°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	12.03 12.37	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	11.42 11.23	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	10.68 10.28

*Compounds marked are known in literature

TABLE II

Chlorophenoxyacetylglucyl derivatives.

R'	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
I. R = p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .								
C ₆ H ₅ .	210-11°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	12.34	12.15	190-91°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	11.20	11.50
3, 4-(O-CH ₂ -O)=C ₆ H ₃ .	177-70°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	10.83	10.78	231-32°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	10.35	9.90
p-Me ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .	230°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	14.60	14.42	191-92°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	12.99	13.24
m-OH.C ₆ H ₄ .	233-34°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.84	11.61	248°(d)	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	10.97	10.60
p-MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .	205-206°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.00	11.19	178°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	10.57	10.24
p-NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .	180-92°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	15.38	15.53	201°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	13.70	14.18
C ₆ H ₅ .CH=CH.	208-209°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	11.49	11.31	206°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₄	9.97	10.35
C ₃ H ₇ N-2.	187-88°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	16.22	16.16	186-87°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₄	14.87	14.70
C ₃ H ₇ N-3.	190-91°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	16.10	16.16	182°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₄	14.60	14.70
C ₃ H ₇ N-4.	182°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	15.81	16.16	225°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	14.45	14.70
C ₉ H ₉ N-2.	196-98°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	14.16	14.13	213°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₄	12.57	12.99
III. R = 2,4,5-Cl ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ .								
					245-47°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃	10.26	10.14
					216-18°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃	9.40	9.16
					201-202°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	11.99	12.24
					243-44°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	9.47	9.75
					223-23°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	9.43	9.45
					245°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	13.44	13.04
					205°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃	9.24	0.53
					204-206°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	13.30	14.48
					223-24°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	13.03	13.48
					245-46°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	13.34	13.48
					225°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃	11.99	12.93

TABLE III

Chlorophenoxyacetylmethionyl derivatives.

R'.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
			Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.					
			I. R=p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄				III. R=2,4,5-Cl ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ .					
C ₆ H ₅ -	152°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ ClS	10.24	10.01	174°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.63	9.25	182°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	8.90	8.60
3,4-(O.CH ₂ .O)=C ₆ H ₃ -	179°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ ClS	8.95	9.06	173-74°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.70	8.47	205-207°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	8.13	7.89
p-Me ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ -	168°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	11.87	12.11	173°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	11.62	11.27	183-5°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	10.63	10.59
m-OH.C ₆ H ₄ -	206-208°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ ClS	9.90	9.64	164-65°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.37	8.94	158-58°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	8.43	8.33
p-Me.O.C ₆ H ₄ -	146°	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ ClS	9.68	9.34	170°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.98	8.68	180-81°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	8.60	8.10
p-NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -	165°	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	13.02	12.80	191-92°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	12.17	11.94	184°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	11.02	11.13
C ₆ H ₅ .CH=CH-	178-79°	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ ClS	9.38	9.43	185-86°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.98	8.75	140-42°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	8.53	8.16
C ₃ H ₇ N-2.	159-60°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	13.64	13.32	168-70°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	12.76	12.31	167°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	11.50	11.44
C ₃ H ₇ N-3.	165°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	13.47	13.32	167°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	12.76	12.31	182-83°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	12.00	11.44
C ₃ H ₇ N-4.	215°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	12.65	13.32	172°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	12.69	12.31.	169-70°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	11.42	11.44
C ₉ H ₉ N-2.	177°	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	12.25	12.43	180-81°	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	11.45	11.00	178°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₃ S	10.68	10.98

4-Chlorophenoxyacetyl-glycine Hydrazide (Type VI).—To the preceding ethyl 4-chloro-ester (10 g.), dissolved in ethanol (100 ml), 60% hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Ethanol and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed *in vacuo*. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol in colorless laminar crystals, m.p. 154-56°. (Found: C, 46.5; H, 4.98; N, 16.47. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_3Cl$ requires C, 46.6; H, 4.66; N, 16.30%).

Ethyl 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl-glycinate (Type V).—Ethyl glycinate (1.03 g.) in dioxane (15 ml) and DCC (2.1 g.) in dioxane (15 ml) were mixed and 2,4-D (2.21 g.) in dioxane (15 ml) was added to the above mixture and shaken. The product obtained after following the procedure, described earlier, was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum in colorless needles, m.p. 88°. (Found: N, 5.18. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4NCl_2$ requires N, 4.58%).

2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl-glycine Hydrazide (Type VI).—The preceding glycinate (1 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate (1.5 ml) was added. Refluxing and removal of the solvent and excess of hydrazine hydrate provided the crude product which was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 41.23; H, 3.89; N, 14.66. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_3Cl_2$ requires C, 41.1; H, 3.77; N, 14.38%).

Ethyl 2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl-glycinate (Type V).—Ethyl glycinate (6.35 g.) in dioxane (30 ml) and DCC (17 g.) in dioxane (25 ml) were mixed and 2,4,5-T (15.73 g.) in the same solvent (30 ml) was added to the above mixture. Following the above procedure, the compound was obtained; m.p. 96-98° (ethanol). (Found: N, 4.45. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4NCl_3$ requires N, 4.11%).

2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl-glycine Hydrazide (Type VI).—The preceding glycinate (3.5 g.) in EtOH (50 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate (3 ml) furnished on refluxing and removal of the solvent and excess of hydrazine hydrate, the crude product, m.p. 167° (EtOH). (Found: C, 37.10; H, 3.09; N, 12.86. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_3Cl_3$ requires C, 36.76; H, 3.06; N, 12.86%).

Ethyl 4-Chlorophenoxy-(±)-methionate (Type V).—Ethyl (±)-methionate (12.39 g.) in dioxane (50 ml) and DCC (14.6 g.) in dioxane (50 ml) were mixed and 4-chlorophenoxy-acetic acid (13.10 g.) in dioxane (50 ml) was added. The usual procedure provided the product; b.p. 210-30°/3 mm. [Found (crude product): N, 6.12. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4NClS$ requires N, 4.10%).

4-Chlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionine Hydrazide (Type VI).—Ethyl 4-chlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionate (12.0 g.) in ethanol (120 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) were refluxed. The solvent and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed *in vacuo* to furnish the product; m.p. 115-17° (EtOH). (Found: C, 47.61; H, 5.79; N, 12.20. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3N_3ClS$ requires C, 47.07; H, 5.43; N, 12.67%).

Ethyl 2,4-Dichlorophenoxy-(±)-methionate (Type V).—The product was obtained from ethyl (±)-methionate (3.54 g.) in dioxane (10 ml), DCC (4.12 g.) in dioxane (10 ml), and 2,4-D (4.42 g.) in the same solvent (10 ml); m.p. 66-67° (ethyl acetate and light petroleum). (Found: N, 3.98. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4NCl_2S$ requires N, 3.68%).

2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionine Hydrazide (Type VI).—Ethyl-2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionate (1.2 g.) in ethanol (25 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate

(3 ml) were refluxed. Removal of ethanol and excess of hydrazine hydrate furnished the product; m.p. 143-44° (EtOH). (Found: C, 42.72; H, 4.43; N, 11.37. C₁₃H₁₇O₃N₃Cl₂S requires C, 42.62; H, 4.64; N, 11.48%).

Ethyl 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxy-(±)-methionate (Type V).—The product was obtained from (ethyl(±)-methionate (7.08 g.) in dioxane (25 ml), DCC (8.4 g.) in dioxane (25 ml), and 2,4,5-T (10.78 g.) in dioxane (30 ml). The procedure was the same as described earlier for this type of compounds. The product was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and light petroleum, m.p. 108-109°. (Found: N, 3.77. C₁₃H₁₆O₄NCl₃S requires N, 3.37%).

TABLE IV

Results of screening for inhibition of *in vitro* growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v at a dilution of 1:10,000.

Serial number.	Aldehydes used for reaction with acid-hydrazides.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyacetyl derivative.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyacetyl glycol derivative.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionyl derivative.	2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl derivative.	2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl glycol derivative.	2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionyl derivative.	2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl derivative.	2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl glycol derivative.	2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionyl derivative.	Number of active compounds.	Activity of aldehydes by themselves.
1	Benzaldehyde											+
2	Piperonal											+
3	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde										2	+
4	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde						—	×	—	—	3	+
5	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde											±
6	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzaldehyde	—	—		—	—	—	—			6	×
7	Cinnamaldehyde											+
8	Pyridine-2-aldehyde	—	—		—	—	—	—				+
9	Pyridine-3-aldehyde	—	—		—	—	—	—				+
10	Pyridine-4-aldehyde	—	—		—	—	—	—				+
11	Quinoline-2-aldehyde	::	—	::	::	::	::	::	::	::		+
12	Acid	::	×	::	::	×	::	×	×	×		
13	Ethyl ester	::	::	::	×	—	×	×	×	×		
14	Hydrazide	—	::	::	—	—	::	—	::	—		
No. of active compounds (columnwise)		5	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	41

Legend: — indicates complete inhibition of *in vitro* growth at 1:10,000 dilution.
 + indicates "no inhibition" of *in vitro* growth at 1:10,000 dilution.
 ± indicates partial inhibition of *in vitro* growth at 1:10,000 dilution.
 × Compounds not tested or not prepared.

Note: Ethyl esters of *p*-chlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-valine, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-valine, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetyl-(—)-leucine were also tested, but none showed any inhibition.

Out of the 119 compounds (i.e. 98 hydrazones, 3 acids, 9 esters and 9 hydrazides) tested, 41 inhibited the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at 1:10,000 dilution.

2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionine Hydrazide (Type VI).—Ethyl 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetyl-(±)-methionate (15 g.) in ethanol (200 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) were refluxed. Excess of hydrazine hydrate and ethanol were removed *in vacuo*. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 171-72°. (Found: C, 39.04; H, 3.84; N, 10.68. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3N_3Cl_3S$ requires C, 38.95; H, 3.99; N, 10.48%).

Aldehyde-condensation Products of the Hydrazines (Types IV & VII).—The hydrazones were obtained by refluxing equimolar quantities of hydrazides and aldehydes in ethanol; yields were good (*vide* Tables I-III).

*Pharmacology

The antitubercular activities of these compounds were tested by the surface culture technique, using the virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v with ethylene glycol or ethanol as the solvent; serial dilutions of the drug were prepared in Youman's media and sterilised at 15 lb. for 20 min. A thin film of the *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v, taken from a 12 to 14 day culture of the organisms by a 4-mm loop, was gently floated on to the surface of the drug dilutions. The tubes were paraffin-sealed and incubated at 37°. Suitable solvent controls were run at the same time. The extent of surface growth was recorded at weekly intervals. The significant results, as seen at the end of 3 weeks, are indicated.

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